

Original Research

The Impact of Moral Hazard Uncertainty and Macro Indicators on the Long-Term Volatility Transmission Pattern of the Investment Sector

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Abstract

In economics, corruption is defined as exploiting public power to achieve personal goals. The importance of international trade, on the one hand, and the ethical complexities in it, on the other hand, doubles the necessity of carefully examining the relationship between these two categories. In this research, an attempt has been made to examine the relationship between foreign direct investment and moral risks and uncertainty at the macro level in Iran. Be studied and proven. The current research method is applied, and data collection and analysis are correlational. The statistical population used in this research is foreign direct investment, moral hazard, inflation rate, and exchange rate of Iran. The moral hazard index data have been collected and used through the International Transparency Organization, and the macro index data have been collected and used through the global development indicators. The research sample of these statistics was collected from 2004 to 2023. The results showed that, in this research, the combined Garch-Midas model was used to investigate the effect of macroeconomic uncertainty indicators on the volatility of foreign direct investment returns, and all three uncertainty indicators of exchange rate, inflation rate, and moral hazard have a significant effect on the volatility of foreign direct investment returns. Moreover, moral hazard uncertainty is a leading indicator that affects foreign direct investment in Iran. According to the estimation, macroeconomic uncertainties, especially moral hazard uncertainties, play a significant role in increasing the volatility of foreign direct investment returns.

Keywords: Foreign direct investment, Garch-Midas, moral hazards, uncertainty, macro indicators.

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Introduction

The study of international trade has gained vital importance in the 21st century and plays many crucial roles in the relations between developed and developing countries. This allows businesses in the first world to achieve resource and production efficiencies while expanding into new markets, all while maintaining product and financial competitiveness (Alam & Asfiah, 2024; Bevan, Estrin, & Meyer, 2004). It also fosters development in developing countries and transforms them from being underdeveloped into an active process for the developed (Boddewyn & Brewer, 1994). Foreign direct investment increases capital stock and can enhance the production and productivity of a country (Destek et al., 2023; Straub, 2008).

However, corruption and moral hazard derail the progress of developing countries by hindering the flow of foreign direct investment (FDI) to these countries. Unfortunately, the more underdeveloped a country is, the higher its level of corruption appears to be. Officials are in a mad scramble to pocket as much incoming funding as possible for themselves and their families and friends, even if it comes at the cost of future development (Forson, 2024; Shleifer & Vishny, 1993). Bribery raises the cost of doing business and the cost to consumers and adds to market impenetrability, making the host country less attractive to foreign direct investment. Host country governments are constantly looking to attract more international business, and this can become more difficult if a country is known for attracting the wrong types of multinationals engaged in corrupt practices. This only cements their place among the corrupt set of countries that, for various reasons, hinder good foreign direct investment (Thede & Gustafson, 2017). Being labeled a corrupt country means that the costs and risks associated with foreign direct investment are much higher, creating an additional barrier to capital entering the country. In order for a firm to succeed in a corrupt environment, it must deal with the uncertainty of corruption arising from the obligation of secrecy and the fact that bribing one official does not preclude bribing others to ensure the completion of the governmental process (Amoh et al., 2024; Jetin, Saadaoui, & Ratiarison, 2024; Shleifer & Vishny, 1993). In addition, the agreements between the bribe giver and the bribe taker are not easily enforceable, injecting arbitrariness and uncertainty into the business process (Bardhan, 2017). Therefore, companies face difficulty and risk in understanding the nature of a specific type of corruption in one country compared to its form in other countries (Rugman, 2005; Wu et al., 2023).

Exchange rates and inflation critically influence investment dynamics and the attractiveness of investment destinations. Exchange rate stability reduces uncertainty, aiding investors in predicting returns and minimizing risks associated with currency fluctuations. Conversely, high exchange rate volatility deters investment by increasing the risk of unfavorable currency movements (Ehikioya, 2018). Similarly, inflation impacts investment decisions significantly. Moderate and predictable inflation often reflects a growing economy, encouraging investment by signaling stable economic conditions and potential for returns. In contrast, high and unpredictable inflation erodes purchasing power and distorts price signals, raising the cost of capital and borrowing, which dampens investment. Furthermore, persistent high inflation may lead central banks to increase interest rates to curb inflationary pressures, further discouraging investment

due to the higher cost of financing (Dupor, 2001; Iqbal & Nawaz, 2009; Muhammad et al., 2013; Schito et al., 2024). Thus, maintaining macroeconomic stability through controlled inflation and stable exchange rates is essential for attracting and retaining investments. Policymakers must implement effective monetary policies to ensure a conducive investment environment. This theoretical framework underscores the importance of macroeconomic stability in fostering sustainable investment and economic growth, especially in the context of long-term volatility transmission in the investment sector.

On the other hand, the arbitrariness of corruption is the ambiguity associated with the corruption that occurs in a nation. This is due to the need for more adequately codified rules, leading to changes in what is considered legitimate and what can be legitimized for a price. Arbitrariness also results in well-codified laws being inconsistently interpreted, leading to unsustainable practices, seemingly dependent on the price they are willing to pay (Vásquez Tsuji et al., 2001).

However, the question is, why should domestic countries care about moral hazard, passing laws, and making it illegal to bribe foreign officials? First of all, relying on corrupt practices undermines not only the image of the host country but also their own countries. This can distort a group of investment locations and the country's investment resources. Suppose places become notoriously tainted by attracting dirty foreign direct investment (FDI). In that case, host countries can also be significantly tainted, and their foreign direct investment (FDI) is politely rejected by desirable locations. Therefore, businesses in a developed country can become uncompetitive only if they rely on corrupt practices. In addition, firms that become powerful by corrupting foreign officials become very adept at this practice and try it out in their country so that all the tainted money from bribing officials may come back home (Bath & Gu, 2024; Cuervo-Cazurra, 2016; Guha et al., 2020).

This research paper presents an empirical evaluation of the consequences of moral and macro risks in Iran. A first contribution consistent with the debate about the consequences of moral hazard is to test whether the relationship between foreign investment and moral hazard produces more substantial effects by combining high and low frequencies. The second innovative feature and the central question of these effects are the short-term and long-term relationship provided by several econometric tests and combining GARCH and MIDAS models. One of the major problems is the inability to establish the correct short-term and long-term relationships that determine the relationship between investment and corruption (Akhter, 2004; Guha et al., 2020; Lalountas, Manolas, & Vavouras, 2011; Sandholtz & Gray, 2003).

Literature Review

Several studies have been conducted on moral corruption and risks using the corruption perception index. There is an extensive literature devoted to specific aspects of globalization, namely trade and foreign direct investment, on moral hazard (Ades & Di Tella, 1999; Ades & Tella, 1996; Bonaglia, De Macedo, & Bussolo, 2009; Lambsdorff, 1998; Serra, 2006; Treisman, 2000; Wei & Shleifer, 2000). Researchers have proven in a study that if a highly corrupt country lowers its moral hazard score, the flow of foreign

direct investment will increase for an equivalent increase in human capital (Dutta, Kar, & Saha, 2017). Other researchers have proven that a 1% reduction in the level of corruption leads to an 8-11% increase in foreign direct investment (Hossain, 2016). Other researchers point out in a study that corruption is a serious obstacle to economic growth in the countries of the Middle East and North Africa because it affects investment activities and the flow of foreign direct investment (Fahad & Ahmed, 2016). Other researchers believe that corruption negatively affects inward foreign direct investment (FDI) in post-conflict countries in the long run, and others find that corruption helps attract more foreign direct investment (FDI) (Gossel, 2018).

Yaya et al. (2022) utilize the GARCH-MIDAS model to integrate varying frequency data, enhancing the robustness and accuracy of volatility predictions by combining macroeconomic indicators with high-frequency asset data. Wang et al. (2020) also emphasized that the GARCH-MIDAS model, by integrating data of different frequencies, improves the accuracy and robustness of market volatility predictions, offering a more precise analysis of the impact of macroeconomic indicators.

Although extensive research has been conducted on moral corruption and its impact on FDI, there is a clear need for further studies specifically focusing on Iran. This research aims to bridge that gap by applying the GARCH-MIDAS method to analyze the effects of macroeconomic uncertainties, particularly moral hazard, on FDI volatility in Iran. While previous studies have generally covered the impact of corruption and macroeconomic variables on FDI in various regions, none have specifically addressed the unique economic context of Iran. By extracting high and low frequencies from economic data, this study provides a more detailed understanding of these dynamics, offering novel insights. Incorporating recent studies on GARCH-MIDAS applications in FDI volatility further strengthens the contextual relevance of this research, thus providing valuable information for policymakers and investors. This comprehensive analysis aims to inform more effective strategies for managing economic stability and growth in Iran's investment sector.

Method

The research is applied in terms of its objective and employs a correlation analysis of data with different frequencies for data collection and analysis. The statistical population includes the indices of Foreign Direct Investment (FDI), moral hazards, inflation rate, and exchange rate in Iran. Data for the moral hazard index were collected from Transparency International, while macroeconomic indices were gathered from the World Development Indicators. The study period spans from 2004 to 2023. To address the measurement unit of each variable:

Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) is measured in terms of the rate of return (percentage). The original FDI data were available on an annual basis and transformed into daily data using Cubic Spline Interpolation. This advanced temporal disaggregation technique generates higher-frequency data from lower-frequency observations while preserving realistic trends, allowing for detailed analysis of daily volatility within the GARCH-MIDAS framework.

Exchange Rate data are presented in terms of the Iranian rial per U.S. dollar, and Inflation Rate data are represented as monthly percentage changes. Both variables were converted from their annual reports into monthly frequencies using interpolation to match the other monthly data in the model.

Moral Hazards are represented by an index based on Transparency International data. Although this is a qualitative indicator, it was normalized and scaled to be used alongside quantitative macroeconomic indicators for consistency.

To examine the correlation between data with different frequencies and the relationship between daily data (FDI) and monthly economic data (moral hazards, inflation rate, and exchange rate), the GARCH-MIDAS approach was utilized.

This section introduces and briefly explains the GARCH and GARCH-MIDAS regressions used in the research. GARCH models were developed to address the limitations of ARCH models. These models are estimated using the maximum likelihood method, allowing for the analysis and prediction of market volatility. However, GARCH models assume a uniform frequency of data. Therefore, the GARCH model, when combined with the MIDAS model, enables the differentiation of factors with varying frequencies. This approach allows for predicting stock market volatility without altering the data structure, utilizing two factors: asymmetric effects and volatility effects in both long-term and short-term components. The asymmetric effects refer to the impact of good and bad news, while the volatility effects pertain to the impact of major and minor shocks. Specifically, four scenarios and effects are considered in GARCH-MIDAS: asymmetric effects on the short-term, asymmetric effects on the long-term, severe short-term, and severe long-term effects.

Justification for the GARCH-MIDAS Model: The GARCH-MIDAS model has been specifically designed for analyzing mixed-frequency data, allowing us to simultaneously model both short-term and long-term effects. This model enables us to effectively address the volatility of foreign direct investment (FDI) returns while also considering the impacts of macroeconomic variables, such as exchange rate and inflation uncertainties, thereby facilitating a thorough analysis of the complex relationships between these variables. Compared to alternative models, GARCH-MIDAS provides superior capabilities in managing combined data and identifying temporal patterns, which are critical for this study.

Context of Iran as a Unique Case Study: Iran has been selected as a unique case study due to its specific economic challenges, including significant exchange rate volatility, high inflation, and the impact of international sanctions. These economic conditions make the examination of the relationship between macroeconomic uncertainties and FDI volatility particularly relevant. Furthermore, the distinctive economic and political structure of Iran suggests that the findings of this research may also be beneficial for other countries facing similar challenges, offering insights into the effects of economic uncertainties on foreign investment.

GARCH regression: One of the limitations of the ARCH method is that, due to conditional variance, its value cannot be negative. However, the generalized ARCH

(GARCH) method was introduced to align models with real-world scenarios. This method transforms the ARMA (p, q) model into a GARCH model by considering the variance of the error components (residuals). The general form of this model is described by Equation 1:

$$\delta_t^2 = \beta_0 + \beta_1 u_{t-1}^2 + \dots + \beta_p u_{t-p}^2 + \alpha_1 \delta_{t-1}^2 + \dots + \alpha_q \delta_{t-q}^2 \quad (1)$$

One key feature of using GARCH models is the presence of conditional heteroscedasticity in the data, which includes significant volatility in the variable and conditional heteroscedasticity in the variance.

GARCH-MIDAS regression: MIDAS regression uses data with different frequency intervals in a single regression. In conventional regression models, data with the same frequency must be used; for example, all data related to explanatory and dependent variables must be annual, daily, seasonal, weekly, or monthly. However, MIDAS regression allows for the regression of daily data with monthly or weekly data. The general form of the MIDAS equation is described by Equation 2:

$$Y_t = \alpha_0 + \beta \sum_{j=0}^{j_{\max}} w(j; \theta) L^{\frac{1}{s}} X_t^m + u_t \quad (2)$$

The above equation assigns (t) and (t) to two-time low and high-frequency time units, respectively. The MIDAS method creates a unit called (S), which is defined as a portion of the interval between (t) and (1-t) in a $m = \frac{1}{s}$ manner. The number of observations of the higher frequency variable in the two-time intervals is denoted by (m). However, in the GARCH-MIDAS regression, conditional variance data with different frequencies (daily, monthly, weekly, or quarterly) are used simultaneously (Razmi et al., 2020; Segnon, Gupta, & Wilfling, 2024; Virk et al., 2024).

Results

In this section, in order to provide an overview of the research variables, descriptive statistics related to the research variables are presented in Table 1. The presented descriptive statistics show information about the research variables' central parameters, dispersion parameters, and maximum and minimum criteria. It should be noted that in this study, the rate of return on foreign direct investment is considered as the dependent variable. The study aims to examine the impact of macroeconomic uncertainty indices, including exchange rate uncertainty, inflation rate uncertainty, and uncertainty arising from moral hazards, on the volatility of this variable using the GARCH-MIDAS model. The results presented in Table 1 provide key insights into the behavior of the research variables. The Exchange Rate, with an average value of 1.8760 and a standard deviation of 2.8147, indicates significant volatility, suggesting potential instability in the Iranian economy. The Inflation Rate shows an average of 2.2550, indicating a moderate level of inflation over the study period. The Moral Hazards Index has an average of 1.7639, which suggests a relatively stable perception of moral hazards in investment practices. Lastly, the Foreign Direct Investment shows an average return of 0.7733, which, combined with its high number of observations (7304), suggests a substantial amount of data analyzed,

reflecting ongoing investor interest despite uncertainties in the macroeconomic environment.

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics of Variables

	Observations	Average	Maximum	Minimum	Standard deviation
Exchange Rate	240	1.8760	4.4241	0.0615	2.8147
Inflation	240	2.2550	4.8407	0.8493	1.4121
Moral hazards	240	1.7639	3.5689	0.5690	0.2021
Foreign direct investment	7304	0.7733	1.9962	0.3538	0.3893

According to the conventional approach in estimating time series models and to avoid spurious regressions, the stationarity of the research variables must first be tested based on standard unit root tests (Yin, Liu, & Jin, 2020). The results of the augmented Dickey-Fuller test and the Phillips-Perron test are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Results of the Augmented Dickey-Fuller and Phillips-Perron Tests

	Generalized Dickey-Fuller	Phillips-Perron	Critical value	Result
Exchange Rate	-19.31	-66.17	-3.86	stationary
Inflation	-5.25	-6.24	-3.88	stationary
Moral hazards	-7.83	-9.04	-3.44	stationary
Foreign direct investment	-7.68	-8.70	-3.88	stationary

In Table 2, given that the absolute values of the augmented Dickey-Fuller and Phillips-Perron test statistics for all variables exceed the critical values at the 5% level, the null hypothesis (Ho) of non-stationarity is rejected. In other words, all the variables under study are stationary at the level.

Calculation of Macroeconomic Uncertainty Indices: Macroeconomic uncertainty can be interpreted as the inability of agents to predict the outcomes of their decisions accurately. This study examines the impact of macroeconomic variable uncertainty on the volatility of foreign direct investment (FDI) return indices. In this context, three macroeconomic uncertainty indices are utilized: exchange rate uncertainty, inflation rate uncertainty, and uncertainty arising from moral hazards. The most common method used to calculate the uncertainty of economic variables is the Generalized Autoregressive Conditional Heteroskedasticity (GARCH) model. In these models, conditional autoregressive variance is used as a proxy for the uncertainty of economic and financial variables (Yin, Liu, & Jin, 2020).

This study calculates the uncertainties of exchange rates, inflation rates, and moral hazards using GARCH family models. After examining the stationarity of the variables using time series econometric methods, the best model was selected based on the Schwarz Bayesian Criterion and the correlogram. Subsequently, the presence or absence of ARCH effects was examined using the ARCH-LM statistic. Table 3 shows the results of the ARCH-LM test for the estimated autoregressive models.

Table 3. Results of ARCH-LM Tests

	F-statistic	F-probability	Chi-square statistic	Chi-square probability
Exchange Rate	33.69	0.0000	33.61	0.0000
Inflation	17.68	0.0001	15.15	0.0001
Moral hazards	49.16	0.0001	14.97	0.0001
Foreign direct investment	18.06	0.0000	18.01	0.0000

The results in Table 3 indicate that the null hypothesis of no ARCH effect is rejected at the 99% confidence level, and the alternative hypothesis of the presence of an ARCH effect is accepted. Subsequently, based on the Akaike and Schwarz Bayesian criteria, the (1,1) GARCH model was used to calculate the uncertainty of the mentioned variables, utilizing the conditional variance computed by this model. The conditional variance calculated by the (1,1) GARCH model has been used as a proxy for market uncertainty. Finally, the GARCH-MIDAS model is estimated.

Table 4. Results of GARCH MIDAS Model Estimations Using Uncertainty Indices

Moral hazards	Inflation	Exchange Rate	
0.0004	0.0057815	0.0003	μ
-0.2460	-0.11615	-0.1660	α
-0.8930	-0.88385	-0.7290	β
-3.8800	-0.000014055	-0.0220	θ
5.9000	0.6432	4.8200	ω
-15984.2	-12016.2	-15872.5	AIC
-15948.4	-11974.8	-15655	BIC

Discussion

The research findings indicate that this study used a combination of high-frequency data for the GARCH model and low-frequency MIDAS data. The GARCH-MIDAS model collects data from various sources and at different frequencies. The information analysis in this model uses econometric methods that consider the correlation between data of different frequencies and model their impacts on return volatility. In particular, the GARCH-MIDAS model is capable of estimating both short-term and long-term coefficients, allowing for a nuanced understanding of how different macroeconomic factors influence volatility over varying time horizons. Calculating macroeconomic uncertainty indices, including exchange rate uncertainty, inflation rate uncertainty, and moral hazards, was performed based on GARCH models. After examining the stationarity of the variables, the best model was selected based on the Schwarz-Bayesian criterion and the correlogram. The presence of ARCH effects was examined using the ARCH-LM test. The results in Table 3 show that the hypothesis of no ARCH effect is rejected at the 99% confidence level, and the presence of an ARCH effect is accepted. Finally, the (1,1) GARCH model was used to calculate the uncertainty of the variables, and the conditional variance was calculated as a proxy for uncertainty in the markets. In this study, to examine the impact of economic uncertainty indices on the volatility of foreign direct investment

returns, three GARCH-MIDAS models of exchange rate, inflation rate, and moral hazard were used as explanatory variables. As previously stated, in the GARCH-MIDAS model, the conditional variance of the dependent variable in this study, foreign direct investment returns, is specified as short-term and long-term components.

In this model, (μ) represents the intercept in the mean equation, while (α) and (β) are parameters of the short-term component of the conditional variance. (α) indicates the impact of current events on the conditional variance of the dependent variable, and (β) represents the persistence of volatility (the impact of past events). The closer (β) is to one, the more significant the previous information is compared to current information; in other words, the effects of previous shocks and volatility will have more remarkable persistence. In all three models, the coefficients (α) and (β) are estimated to be negative and significant, with (β) being somewhat close to one, indicating the importance of previous information over current information. (ω) is the model's weighting (smoothing) parameter, estimated to be statistically significant. The main objective of this research is to examine the impact of macroeconomic uncertainty indices on the volatility of investment returns. The parameter (θ) shows the macroeconomic uncertainty variable's effect on the conditional variance's long-term component. The significant estimation of this coefficient in the three models under review indicates the impact of macroeconomic uncertainty indices on the volatility of the investment sector's returns. However, in the model where moral hazard uncertainty is used as an explanatory variable, this coefficient is significantly larger than in other models. In other words, as a macroeconomic uncertainty index, moral hazard uncertainty significantly impacts the volatility of investment returns. This indicates market participants' attention and the investment market's higher sensitivity to domestic uncertainty. Furthermore, based on the Akaike and Schwarz Bayesian criteria, using moral hazard uncertainty as an economic uncertainty index in modeling investment index volatility shows the best performance.

Based on the results obtained, the questions were answered. This finding is consistent with the research of other scholars (Allen, Dharmapala, & Puhani, 2021; Djankov et al., 2005; Han, Javorcik, & Wei, 2020; Kaufmann & Mautner, 2005; McWilliams, Siegel, & Wood, 2019; Zhao, 2006). There is also substantial evidence showing this multi-faceted relationship (Apostolov, 2016; Busse & Hefeker, 2007; Jin et al., 2019; Osei & Kim, 2020; Pirju et al., 2023; Kian Poor et al., 2021; Kian Poor et al., 2020). The significant impact of moral hazard uncertainty on FDI volatility suggests that investors may perceive increased risks when faced with domestic economic uncertainties. This heightened sense of risk can lead to greater fluctuations in investment returns, as investors adjust their expectations based on the perceived stability of the market. Understanding these dynamics is crucial for stakeholders in the investment sector, as it highlights the need for effective risk management strategies to mitigate the adverse effects of economic uncertainties.

Moreover, the findings underscore the importance of addressing moral hazards in policy-making. Policymakers should consider implementing robust regulatory frameworks that enhance transparency and accountability within the economic landscape. By reducing moral hazards, the government can foster a more stable investment

environment, thereby attracting foreign direct investment and supporting economic growth. Additionally, investors are encouraged to closely evaluate market conditions and potential moral hazards when making investment decisions to optimize their strategies in light of the identified uncertainties.

One of the limitations of this study is the research years, as data on moral hazards before 2004 is not collectible. Another area for improvement is that this study only shows the correlation between uncertainty indices and return volatility. Further research using causal analysis methods is needed to prove a causal relationship. Further research should be conducted in other countries with different levels of uncertainty and economic structures.

Additionally, more complex models can be used to examine the dynamics of foreign direct investment return volatility and moral hazards in response to uncertainty. Therefore, to increase the efficiency of the public sector and, ultimately, the country's progress, anti-corruption policies should be considered, and this part of the country's economy should be seriously examined and studied. Foreign investment can be attracted by reducing uncertainty and moral hazards in the economy, and economic growth can be enhanced.

Conclusion

In economics, corruption is defined as the abuse of public power for personal gain. This destructive phenomenon not only directly leads to the reduction of GDP but also has profound adverse effects on income distribution, human development indicators, and generally on countries' economic and social structure. In addition, corruption and moral hazard can jeopardize the credibility and competitiveness of a country in the global arena and prevent the attraction of foreign investment and economic progress. Among the indicators of macroeconomic uncertainty, the uncertainty of moral hazard has the most significant effect on the fluctuations of the efficiency of Iran's foreign direct investment sector. This finding is significant because it shows the high sensitivity of the capital market to issues related to ethics and illegal and unethical behaviors in Iran's business environment. In other words, the capital market reacts more to internal uncertainties and moral hazards, which can be due to the increase in unpredictable risks and the decrease in trust in the stability and transparency of the market. These findings emphasize the importance of proper management of economic uncertainties and especially moral risks in Iran. Moral hazard, which includes unethical behavior in the business environment, can significantly affect the volatility of investment returns. Policymakers and economic managers in Iran should pay special attention to improving transparency and reducing ethical risks in financial markets. The implementation of stricter laws and more careful supervision can lead to the reduction of this type of risk and increase the confidence of investors. In addition, the results of this research can guide foreign investors to pay more attention to the effects of economic uncertainties in Iran in their decisions and formulate appropriate strategies to manage the risks associated with these uncertainties. Especially in countries like Iran, where there are higher moral hazards, investors should take more measures to assess risks and predict market fluctuations. In sum, the results of this research not only help to understand better the dynamics affecting the return of foreign investments in Iran but also provide solutions to reduce the adverse effects of economic

uncertainties that can lead to improving the stability and efficiency of Iran's financial markets. Especially the emphasis on lowering ethical risks can play a crucial role in creating a more stable and moral environment for foreign direct investments in Iran. Paying attention to these issues can attract more foreign investments and improve the country's economic situation because the increase in inflation and fluctuations in the exchange rate can result from moral hazards such as corruption and abuse of public power for personal gain. These moral hazards cause economic instability and a lack of public trust in the country's policies and management. Economic instability and fluctuations in exchange rates due to inflation can increase risk and reduce predictability in financial markets, hindering foreign direct investment attraction to Iran. Therefore, as a primary factor, moral hazard causes a decrease in trust and an increase in fluctuations in the exchange rate and inflation, which directly contribute to hindering the attraction of foreign direct investment to Iran.

Abbreviations (Nomenclature)

δ_t^2	Conditional variance at time t
β_0	Intercept term
β_i	Coefficients for lagged squared residuals
α_j	Coefficients for lagged conditional variances
u_{t-i}^2	Squared residuals (errors) from the mean equation at lag i
q	Order of the GARCH component
p	Order of the lagged squared residuals
Y_t	Dependent variable at time t
α_0	Intercept term
β	Coefficient for the explanatory variable
\sum	Summation symbol
j_{max}	Maximum lag
$\omega(j; \theta)$	Weight function with parameters θ
L^m	Lag operator applied m times
X_t	Explanatory variable at time t
u_t	Error term at time t

Author Contributions

All authors contributed equally to the conceptualization, methodology, software, validation, formal analysis, investigation, resources, data curation, writing original draft preparation, writing review & editing, visualization, supervision, project administration, and funding acquisition of this research.

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